

Interview with Otomania, Vocaloid Composer

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

Otomania, also known as Zenjitsuyoyaku-P —前日予約 P—, is a Japanese music producer, composer, and performer involved in the Project Diva and Vocaloid productions —virtual singers and dancers that have become a global phenomenon. He has worked on musical productions in Japan and, together with the manga artist known as “Tamago,” created a comic related to Miku Hatsune’s derivative version —fan-made adaptations of Vocaloid characters—, Hachune Miku, in which he also participated in the creation process.

Composer Otomania with the bass guitar he used during his visit to Granada

In addition, he composes and produces music for video games, both related to Project Diva —the games featuring Miku and other virtual Vocaloid divas— as well as works entirely outside the project.

This interview was made possible thanks to Otomania’s visit to Spain and the concert he gave on April 30 in Granada —which he kindly repeated the following day— as part of his attendance at Ficzone 2016 in the Nasrid city.

He also held a lecture and a Vocaloid workshop, explaining aspects of his work, how some of the software tools function, what can be achieved with them, and sharing part of his experience working with Vocaloid.

His collaboration with the franchise is almost entirely tied to the virtual diva Miku Hatsune, composing or producing songs for her, such as the world-famous *Ievan Polkka*, a version of the traditional Finnish song of the same name —a global hit.

Otomania also works with the Vocaloids Rin and Len, Kaito, and Luka Megurine —the latter of which we also saw perform in concert alongside Miku Hatsune in Granada.

The artist also demonstrated his skills on the bass, playing alongside the Vocaloids and interacting with them during the concert. You can see him here, testing the bass he used in Granada.

Otomania also participated in a party at the Granada pop, rock, and electronic music venue Polaroid, where the illustrator Yoshiyuki Sadamoto —whom we have also interviewed— attended as a special guest.

Interview with Otomania

Cool Japan: Vocaloid is a global pop culture phenomenon. How does it feel to be part of that whirlwind?

Otomania: I am honoured to have been part of it. I'm very happy with the importance Vocaloid has gained, the fame of characters like Miku, and that I could contribute with my work to this situation.

Cool Japan: Where did your interest in the Vocaloid project come from?

Otomania: At first, I didn't plan to get involved, but once I saw the tools available for development, I tried doing something myself. I liked the work I did, and apparently people liked it too. Vocaloid is a tool that gives you a lot of freedom; you can do almost anything, like having the virtual singer modulate their voice, pronunciation, and even change gender...

Cool Japan: How did your experience with Project Diva begin? Where did your approach come from?

Otomania: The request came to me almost directly from Sega. When they saw what I had done with Miku Hatsune, working with her voice, they asked me to create sounds and phrases for the final version of the game as well.

Cool Japan: Was it difficult to start on such a big project, with so much impact?

Otomania: It wasn't very difficult for me, but of course, I wanted to live up to a project of this importance, so I gave it my all and I'm very grateful for the opportunity to have been part of it.

Cool Japan: Besides Vocaloid, do you use any other software for music composition? Which editing programs do you use?

Official SEGA artwork featuring Miku Hatsune and Luka Megurine performing together (two Vocaloids with whom Otomania works)

Otomania: I began composing with digital tools ten years ago, and I started using Vocaloid nine years ago. Apart from the Vocaloid software suite itself, I also frequently use Cubase, as well as VST Instruments and Native Instruments (as DTS software tools).

Cool Japan: What is your favourite instrument? In electronic composition, which tool do you feel most comfortable with?

Otomania: I play several instruments. I can also play the guitar and keyboard. But my favourite has always been the bass. You'll be able to see me playing it at the Miku Hatsune concert I'm giving right here in Granada! In any case, I'm quite flexible when it comes to these matters.

I started playing the bass many years ago, but I won't tell you how many, because I'd have to tell you my age —and that's a secret [laughs]. Playing instruments and composing have been my passion since I was very young.

As for electronic tools... I've become very accustomed to Vocaloid software and the Native Elements software suites.

Cool Japan: Have you worked on other projects related to the video game industry? If so, could you mention some of your work?

Otomania: Yes, I have worked for the Japanese company Marvelous Entertainment, composing music for video games. To name one, *Half-Minute Hero*. In that game, I was one of the composers contributing to its soundtrack. I also worked on the PlayStation 2 game *Toru no Hoshi – Aerial Planet*, developed by Nippon Ichi.

At present, I am working on online video games in the musical field. I have also worked as a scriptwriter on the manga *Hachune Miku no Nichijō Roipara!*.

Half Minute Hero, one of the video games Otomania has contributed to, and Miku Hachune, illustration by Tamago, from the manga they created together

Cool Japan: When you work on a music video or a video game related to Project Diva or Vocaloid, do you personally create the choreography or align the dance with the music? What is the procedure?

Otomania: In principle, it's a task I could do, but since it's very labour-intensive, it's handled by someone else who specializes in that work.

Cool Japan: What are your musical tastes? Do you have a preferred genre?

Otomania: Enka is one of the genres I like the most. I also enjoy similar music related to it, even earlier pieces performed with traditional Japanese and Western instruments. I also really like music from the 1970s and 1980s, although not any specific genre, and I enjoy singers from later periods as well, such as Ayumi Hamasaki or the group Ikimonogakari.

Cool Japan: Have you travelled in Europe before? Have you been to Spain before? What did you like the most about our country?

Otomania: This is my first time in Spain, and I haven't been able to see much, but from my visit to Granada I can tell you that the Alhambra caught my attention the most.

Otomania during his visit to the Alhambra and the Albaicín in Granada

Cool Japan: To conclude... Are you familiar with the Cool Japan project? What do you find most “cool” about Japan?

Otomania: I really like the mentality of young Japanese people nowadays. People who enjoy their work and pursue their goals with passion, living the way they envisioned. I share the same interests as this kind of people.

Acknowledgements

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Otomania signing a fan's copy of *Project Diva* for PS Vita during his lecture

Thanks to Otomania himself, who assisted us effortlessly in both Japanese and English, for his kindness and great character. A professional truly passionate about his work, who shone during the concert alongside Miku Hatsune and Luka Megurine.

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Sources

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